

TENDENCIES OF PROVIDING THE INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND WORK

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11486903>

Abstract: the article analyzes the achievements of modern civilization by modernizing all spheres of social life in the spirit of nationalism according to the criteria of universal development, the strategy of development, the way of development.

Key words: science, education, integration, innovation, humanitarianism.

Wide application of the achievements of scientific and technical development in the social life of the 20th century brought about fundamental changes in the content and essence of reproductive and innovative types of activity. Increasing attention to the human factor and the desire to fully satisfy his needs has made the creation of innovations and their introduction a vital necessity, and has led to the emergence of special institutional structures that serve to conduct innovative activities. Scientific institutions engaged in fundamental and applied sciences, various associations, creation of a system of legal, economic and social institutions for the management of science, material and spiritual stimulation, and the direct implementation of new ideas and solutions in society. had a positive effect on the formation of the innovation space.

It is natural that the innovative activity carried out within the framework of special institutional structures equipped on a scientific and technical basis will have a good effect, especially for the creation and justification of an innovative idea and a conceptual basis, the activity carried out individually and holistically is of great importance. Based on practical experiences, it can be said that in order to achieve efficiency in innovative activities, the substantiation of these ideas, and the direct connection with practice in finding a solution are considered to be appropriate factors. Such efforts are the reason for the growing trend of organic connection between science and production. The introduction of information technologies into all aspects of creative activity creates favorable conditions for the interdependence of reproductive and innovative activities, increases the effectiveness of finding a clear technological solution of a theoretical idea as an expression of a new idea and implementing it directly into practice.

It is self-evident that drawing conclusions from the lessons of history and managing social life based on democratic and humanitarian criteria is desirable in all respects. The formation of a new worldview called for finding ways to rationally organize social and cultural activities. As a product of such a new way of thinking, the full implementation of human rights and freedoms, and the protection of his interests were rated as a priority. In order to consistently implement this, first of all, it was necessary to determine the issue of ensuring social development and management in accordance with the spirit of the times.

The desire to interpret society and human philosophy from the point of view of a new worldview required specific methodological principles of socio-cultural development. The idea of a gradual process of social development forms the basis of such a worldview. Consequently, it helps to interpret the laws of the circular movement of society's life.

Gradual development is based on the laws of development of both natural and social existence. After all, the internal balance of the natural being is preserved only when social events take place in harmony, and there is an opportunity to change it and subjugate it to human interests. But gradual development is a long process. Man tries to speed up this process by using the capabilities of his intelligence. After all, in this way, the opportunities to meet the ever-growing needs of a person can be expanded.

The use of various methods in managing social processes with the help of socio-cultural potential is a legitimate process. For example, in the recent past, there was a tendency to implement development by means of revolutionary leaps, as a result of which serious problems, unprecedented in the history of mankind, arose.

In conclusion, the development strategy of the new development path of our country envisages the assimilation of the achievements of modern civilization by modernizing all spheres of social life in the spirit of nationalism according to the criteria of universal development. Because the destructive effect of the achievements of modern social development on national-cultural traditions and values is observed, and its consequences leave their traces in the consciousness of young people. The consumer society enables the transition to the innovative stage with the rise of the spiritual and moral culture of young people.

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